

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF COMMERCIAL SAMPLES OF THIRAM

Sample wt %	% Thiram present	% Thiram found		Relative standard deviation	Accuracy %
		Proposed method	Fischer method		
Thiram (100)	0.100	0.099	0.096	0.71	1.00
	0.200	0.198	0.198	0.35	1.00
	0.400	0.399	0.398	0.75	0.25
	0.600	0.597	0.596	0.26	0.50
	0.800	0.799	0.798	0.09	0.13
Thiram (75)	0.100	0.0987	0.097	0.58	1.33
	0.200	0.1986	0.196	0.29	0.70
	0.400	0.3980	0.398	0.14	0.50
	0.600	0.5960	0.597	0.09	0.66
	0.800	0.7990	0.798	0.07	0.13

Comparison of sensitivity: According to Lowen³, Cullen⁴ and Verma⁵ minimum of 15.9, 31.8 and 25 μg of thiram equivalent to 10, 20 and 15.72 μg of CS_2 evolved can be determined respectively, but according to the present method 5 μg of thiram equivalent to 3.144 μg of CS_2 can be determined. Moreover, this method is simple direct and less time-consuming.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.M.) thanks the Bureau of Police Research and Development, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. W. FISCHER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 137, 90.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed. Longman, London, 1978, p. 738.
3. W. K. LOWEN, *J. Assoc. Off. Agric. Chem.*, 1953, 36, 484.
4. T. E. CULLEN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 36, 221.
5. N. VERMA, Ph.D. Thesis, Punjabi University, 1985.

Thin Layer Chromatographic Separation of some Sulpha Drugs using Acetylacetone as a Coupling Agent

RAJEEV JAIN* and ASHA BHATIA

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University,
Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 27 March 1989, revised 24 January 1990,
accepted 24 January 1990

SULPHA drugs have been separated by various chromatographic procedures, e.g. paper chromatography¹ and thin layer chromatography². Poethke and Kize³ employed two-dimensional tlc on alumina plates but all the sulpha drugs investigated could not be separated. Wehrh⁴ reported the separation of sulpha drugs using *N*-(1-naphthyl)-

ethylenediammonium dichloride as a coupling agent. Sulpha drugs in amounts upto 4 μg have been quantitatively estimated by Wagner and Wandel⁵ using chloroform-n-butanol-light petroleum (1:1:10, v/v). Twenty sulphonamides were separated on thin layers of ion-exchangers in different solvent systems⁶. Various new chromogenic reagents for the detection of sulphonamides on tlc plates have been reported⁷. Srivastava *et al.*⁸ separated ten closely related sulpha drugs on silica gel impregnated with cadmium acetate.

The present paper describes the resolution and identification of some sulpha drugs in the form of their acetylacetone derivatives. Thus a mixture of sulpha drugs was converted into the coupled products on thin-layer plates and subsequently chromatographed. In a mixture of nine sulpha drugs it was possible to characterise 0.1–0.2 μg of each drug in the form of its coupled product.

Experimental

All the solvents used were freshly dried and distilled. Tlc-glass plates (20×20 cm) for supporting the layer were used. An ascending irrigation technique was employed.

Preparation of coupled products: A sulpha drug (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. A cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol, 0.69 g) was added to it and the resulting diazonium salt was filtered into a cooled solution of sodium acetate (10.0 g) and acetylacetone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). The solid product was then washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals: sulphaphenazole, m.p. 205°; sulphamethiazole, 225°; sulphadimidine, 190°; sulphamethoxazole, 175°; sulphathiazole, 155°; sulphacetamide, 155°; metacalfin, 130°; phthalylsulphathiazole, 210°; sulphasomidine, 180°.

Adsorbents: The following adsorbents were employed: A, silica gel-G (E. Merck, throughout); B, silica gel-G with 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide; C, silica gel-G with 1% Triton-X 100; D, silica gel-G with 1% sodium lauryl sulphate; E, silica gel-G with 1% cupric acetate; F, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 ; G, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 and 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide; H, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 and 1% Triton-X 100; I, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 and 1% sodium lauryl sulphate.

Procedure: Tlc plates (0.5 mm thickness) of the above mentioned adsorbents were prepared and spotted with the solutions of coupled products of sulpha drugs in acetone. After air-drying these plates at room temperature, they were irrigated with suitable solvents. It took about 30 min to run the solvent system 16 cm. Yellow or orange spots could be observed without any visualising agent. However, for dilute solutions (below 0.1 μg) the spots could be visualised

by exposing them to iodine vapours. Alongside the authentic sample of the coupled product of sulphadiazole, the solution of the diazotised sulphadiazole in acetone ($10^{-6}M$) was spotted and at the same position a solution of acetylacetone (equivalent 1.0 mol of sulphadiazole) in acetone was also applied. Both the samples came in sequence and gave similar R_f values.

Results and Discussion

When the sulphadiazole drugs were spotted as mixtures or individually and were then converted on the plates into their coupled products with acetylacetone, on subsequent irrigation, they were distinctly resolved. Thus a mixture of nine sulphadiazole drugs in the form of their coupled products was readily resolved and their sequence on silica gel-G plate was as follows: sulphadiazole < sulphadiazamide < phthalylsulphathiazole < sulphadiazimidine < sulphamethizole < sulphosomidine < sulphathiazole < metacalfin < sulphamethoxazole.

The best solvent system was found to be dichloromethane-carbon tetrachloride-methanol (45 : 50 : 5, v/v) and the best adsorbent system being silica gel-G impregnated with 20% $CaCO_3$ and 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide. In these systems all the nine coupled products of sulphadiazole drugs could be separated. Their sequence on the developed chromatogram was as follows: sulphadiazole ($R_f=0.12$) < phthalylsulphathiazole (0.28) < sulphadiazamide (0.40) < sulphasomidine (0.50) < sulphamethizole (0.62) < metacalfin (0.78) < sulphadiazimidine (0.86) < sulphamethoxazole (0.93) < sulphathiazole (0.99). In all these cases coupled products could be observed directly as yellow spots and there was no necessity for a spray reagent as in case of sulphadiazole drugs alone.

On the other hand, good separation could not be achieved using silica gel-G impregnated with Triton-X 100, sodium lauryl sulphate and cupric acetate (with or without 20% $CaCO_3$)—either there was no clear separation or profuse tailing occurred with the majority of the drugs. Mixtures of polar solvents when employed for irrigation of plates resulted in either long tailing or highly diffused spots. Non-polar solvents and their mixtures produced excellent resolution of compounds. Thin coatings (0.5 mm) of the adsorbents produced good results. In general, it was observed that mobility of compounds on silica gel-G impregnated with 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide was greatly increased when compared with silica gel-G or silica gel-G+20% $CaCO_3$.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. R. P. Bhatnagar, Head of the Department, for facilities.

References

1. G. THOMAS, J. ROLAND and A. V. BULCKE, *J. Pharm. Belg.*, 1950, 15, 263; R. BOBINSON, *Nature*

- (London), 1951, 168, 512; A. E. STEEL, *Nature (London)*, 1951, 168, 877; G. L. SAN and A. J. ULTEETR, *Nature (London)*, 1952, 169, 586; H. G. BRAY, H. J. LAKE and W. V. THORPE, *J. Biochem. (Tokyo)*, 1951, 48, 400.
2. E. ADAM and C. L. LAPIERO, *J. Pharm. Belg.*, 1964, 19, 79; K. ADANK and U. W. HAMMER SCHMIDT, *Chimia*, 1964, 18, 361; A. R. ALHA and U. R. LINDFERA, *Ann. Med. Exp. Penn.*, 1959, 37, 149; W. AWE and U. H. G. TRACHT, *Pharm. Zig. (Frankfurt)*, 1963, 108, 1365; BR. BACHLER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 45, 309; *Pharm. Acta Helv.*, 1964, 29, 457; *Chimia*, 1963, 17, 257; I. BAYER, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1964, 16, 237; K. H. BYER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1963, 75, 1136; S. KLEIN and B. T. KHO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1962, 51, 967; J. ZARNACK and U. S. PFEIFFER, *Pharmazie*, 1964, 19, 216; U. R. CIERI, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, 49, 493; L. LEPRI, P. C. DESIDERI and O. HEIMLER, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1979, 169, 271.
 3. W. POETHKE and U. W. KIZE, *Pharm. Zentralhalle*, 1964, 103, 95.
 4. A. WEHRH, *Can. Pharm. J. Sci.*, 1964, 97, 208.
 5. G. WAGNER and U. J. WANDEL, *Pharmazie*, 1966, 21, 105.
 6. L. LEPRI, P. G. DESIDERI, M. LANDIMI and G. TANTURH, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1975, 109, 365.
 7. R. R. KRISHNA, P. SIRAJ and C. S. P. SASTRY, *Acta Cienc. Indica Chem.*, 1981, 7, 180; R. JAIN and ASHA BHATIA, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1988, 441, 454.
 8. S. P. SRIVASTAVA, V. K. DUA, R. N. MEHROTRA and R. C. SAXENA, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1979, 176, 145.

On Line Electrochemical Determination of Ascorbic Acid

S. KUMBHAT, C. RAWAT and P. SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 6 June 1989, revised 15 January 1990, accepted 28 February 1990

THERE is a great interest in improving assay procedure for vitamin-C. Presence of electrochemically oxidisable 'enediol' group in ascorbic acid makes it analysable by anodic voltammetry. Various electrochemical methods for determination of ascorbic acid have been reported¹. In the present study we report a simple, fast and sensitive method for the determination of ascorbic acid by high performance liquid chromatography (hplc) with electrochemical detection at glassy carbon electrode (GCE).

Experimental

Differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) and cyclic voltammetric (CV) studies were made on BAS-100 electrochemical analyzer in conjunction with a DMP-40 series digital plotter. GCE served as working electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. A Gilson-HPLC unit with chromatofield electrochemical detector was used for liquid chromatographic determinations. Chromatographic